

ALKYNYLATION REACTIONS OF SOME HETEROATOMIC ALDEHYDES IN THE PARTICIPATION OF PHENYLACETYLENE

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Relevance: In our country, the synthesis of new types of chemicals that have found their place in the world market, the creation of methods for obtaining import-substituting compounds intended for export, and their use in the pharmaceutical, chemical, energy, and construction sectors are urgent tasks, and scientific research is being conducted in this area and certain results are being achieved.

The purpose of the research: To carry out the synthesis of acetylenic alcohols based on the alkyynylation reaction of some aldehydes containing heteroatom substituents in their molecules with phenylacetylene in the presence of a new catalytic system $\text{InBr}_3/\text{Et}_3\text{N}/\text{Et}_2\text{O}$, to systematically study the effect of the molar ratios of the starting materials, reaction duration, temperature, nature of the catalyst and solvents on the product yield, and to determine the efficiency range of the formation of acetylenic alcohols based on the effect of heteroatoms in the aldehyde molecule on the product yield, and to identify their composition, purity, and structure using physicochemical methods.

Methods and techniques: A new generation of acetylenic alcohols was synthesized by alkyynylation of aldehydes containing heteroatom substituents - thiophene-2-carbaldehyde, furan-2-carbaldehyde, and pyridine-3-carbaldehydes with phenylacetylene in the presence of the $\text{InBr}_3/\text{Et}_3\text{N}/\text{Et}_2\text{O}$ catalytic system. The reaction scheme is proposed as follows.

Results: The following acetylenic alcohols - 1-(thiophenyl-2)-3-phenylpropyn-2-ol-1 (1), 1-(furan-2)-3-phenylpropyn-2-ol-1 (2), 1-(pyridin-3)-3-phenylpropyn-2-ol-1 (3) - were synthesized by alkyynylation of aldehydes containing heteroatom substituents in the molecule - thiophene-2-carbaldehyde, furan-2-carbaldehyde, pyridine-3-carbaldehyde with phenylacetylene in the presence of the $\text{InBr}_3/\text{Et}_3\text{N}/\text{Et}_2\text{O}$ catalytic system. The effects of the molar ratios of the starting materials, reaction duration, temperature, nature of the catalyst and solvents on the product yield were systematically studied. Based on the effect of heteroatoms in aldehyde molecules on product yield, the efficiency range of acetylenic alcohols was determined, and their composition, purity, and structure were identified using physicochemical methods.

Conclusions: Based on the results obtained, the most optimal conditions for the synthesis of acetylene alcohols in the $\text{InBr}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{Et}_3\text{N}/\text{Et}_2\text{O}$ catalytic system were found. According to them, the nucleophilic addition reactions of phenylacetylene with selected aldehydes were carried out in a diethyl ether solution in the presence of the catalyst InBr_3 for 120 minutes at a temperature of $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with a 1:1 molar ratio of the starting materials, and the highest yield of acetylene alcohols was determined.